

RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Program Tracking & Evaluation

**2023
Mid-Year
Report**

October 2023

Background

The Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Program aims to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality¹. The Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2) aims to award up to \$200,000 used within a 12-month period to continuously and responsively assess the feasibility of utilizing implementation strategies, community-based interventions, and multi-level partnerships to increase the reach, access, acceptance, uptake, and sustainment of Federal Drug Administration (FDA) authorized/approved COVID-19 diagnostics among vulnerable populations in geographic locations that are underserved in coordination with the National Institute of Health (NIH) supported RADx initiatives². Institutions of higher education, industry, state and local governments, and community-based organizations with the infrastructure to manage such funding are eligible to apply for the RP2 funding. RP2 projects are human subject research studies requiring approval from an Institutional Review Board (IRB).

Objectives

This mid-year evaluation report details the RADx-UP RP2 program’s key evaluation findings that indicate RADx-UP RP2 program outputs, outcomes, productivity, and impacts between January 1, 2023 through June 30, 2023. **Figure 1** summarizes the RP2 evaluation aims.

This report also presents an opportunity for collaboration with RADx-UP, Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC), and NIH stakeholders to establish evaluation feedback loops for identifying and addressing areas of improvement.

Figure 1. RP2 Evaluation Aims

Methods

The Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill (UNC) employs a longitudinal design utilizing a mixed-methods approach. The T&E team collects data on project updates, activities, outcomes, and CDCC support and resources used by the awardees at a minimum of seven time points. Data sources include RP2 program records, project intake surveys, bimonthly evaluation surveys, and a follow-up evaluation survey six months after the closeout of the program. The T&E team is responsible for distributing the bimonthly surveys, analyzing the data, and communicating the results to RP2 leadership and other stakeholders.

Results

Currently, there are **25 total RP2 projects across 7 funding cycles**. For the purpose of this report, project data that has been collected between January 1, 2023 through June 30, 2023* is included in the analyses.

Program Enrollment

As of June 30, 2023 the current funded RP2 projects have enrolled 2,461 participants. Compared to the target enrollment (8,060 participants), **projects have reached 30.5% of their overall target enrollment over the course of their project period**. The target enrollment data were reported by projects at the start of their project period- it is worth noting that many projects were ambitious in their projections of target enrollment totals.

Program Testing

The current funded RP2 projects have administered a total of 2,969 tests of the 16,750 tests planned across active projects, reaching 17.7% of the overall target test count. The target testing data were reported by projects at the start of their project period- it is worth noting that many projects were ambitious in their projections of target enrollment totals. *Note: There is one project that accounts for half of the overall tests planned which is impacting the percentage of tests administered. If we remove this project from this calculation, then there has been a total of 2,267 tests performed of the 7,750 target tests planned, **reaching 29.2% of the overall target test count**.*

*For outcome data (see Outcome and Impacts section), we included projects who completed a Closeout survey between 11.23.22 and 7.21.23 to include more project data.

Challenges and Barriers

The most common challenges reported by the projects (n=11) include enrollment challenges and administrative challenges. *Enrollment challenges* are defined as challenges/delays in recruiting subjects for research once a testing site has been established. *Administrative challenges* are defined as challenges related to release of funding from NIH, hiring and training staff, and non-testing resource procurement.

- Enrollment challenges were largely due to decreased interest in COVID-19 testing, with projects noting testing fatigue and decreased cases of COVID-19.
- Administrative challenges include time taken to finalize budgets and secure funds (e.g. salary support, establishing subcontracts with partners) which in turn has delayed project start, recruitment and enrollment, and staffing shortages.

Outcomes and Impacts

Research Products

As more projects are closing out their RP2 project, they are developing products to report on their findings. Most **products being developed by projects include peer-reviewed publications and conference presentations** (85.7% of projects).

Pilot Award Impact

When asked to rate the impact that the Pilot award had on different aspects of each project's work...

- 100% of projects said that the award improved or significantly **improved team collaboration, research methods, and engagement with community stakeholders**.
- Over 85% of projects said that the award improved or significantly **improved addressing barriers to effective testing in their community**.

CDCC Support and Overall Effectiveness

- The majority of projects (83.3%) are satisfied or very satisfied with the **CDCC's ease of accessing support, overall helpfulness, and promptness of support delivery**.
- Over half of projects (66.7%) feel that the CDCC support services increased their project's **understanding of community engagement approaches**.
- Over half of projects (66.7%) feel that the CDCC support services increased their project's **application of community-engagement approaches in connecting with their project's communities**.

Translational Science Benefits Outcomes

The Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM) is a framework designed to support the assessment of clinical and translational research outcomes to measure clinical and community health impacts³. The T&E team uses the core components of the TSBM to evaluate the impact of the RP2 program in demonstrating* the **clinical, community, economic, and policy benefits** of investing in increased access to COVID-19 testing, vaccination, and community-led engagement initiatives in underserved communities.

Clinical Key Benefits

Over 36% of projects reported at least one project outcome in the Clinical Key Benefit Area. Potential clinical key benefits include:

- Software technologies, investigative procedures to assess trends in COVID-19 testing uptake and track clinical trials; diagnostic procedures/novel testing method to diagnose COVID-19

Community & Public Health Key Benefits

Over 90% of projects reported at least one project outcome in the Community & Public Health Key Benefit Area. Community & Public Health key benefits include:

- COVID-19 testing services/community health services provided for individuals in a community (mobile testing services, handing out of self test kits); assess factors that impact testing uptake; developing/tailoring activities/products for specific populations

Policy Key Benefits

Over 27% of projects reported at least one project outcome in the Policy Key Benefit Area. Potential policy key benefits include:

- Laboratory validation procedures for future simplified approval policies

*Benefits can be classified as demonstrated or potential. Demonstrated benefits are those that have been observed, and potential benefits are those that are expected but not yet demonstrated.

Economic Key Benefits

Over 18% of projects reported at least one project outcome in the Economic Key Benefit Area. Potential economic key benefits include:

- Development of new technologies that may impact commercial products, reduced social and economic costs of acute or chronic disease

Recommendations and Next Steps

Based on the findings from this mid-year report, the T&E team has developed next steps and recommendations for improving the RP2 program and reaching the evaluation goals.

- Address challenges cited by projects, as possible- Projects reported challenges related to participant enrollment, administrative tasks such as funding and staffing, testing reporting, and testing administration.
 - Enrollment challenges were largely due to decreased interest in COVID-19 testing, with projects noting testing fatigue and decreased cases of COVID-19.
 - Administrative challenges included time taken to finalize budgets and secure funds (e.g. salary support, establishing subcontracts with partners) which in turn has delayed project start, recruitment and enrollment, and staffing shortages.
- Maintaining continuous feedback loops between the UNC T&E team, the RP2 Leadership team, and RP2 awardees. Figure 2 illustrates how these feedback loops work amongst the teams- the T&E team reports findings to the RP2 Leadership team, and in turn the RP2 Leadership team communicates this to the RP2 funded projects. Should any questions or concerns arise, the RP2 funded projects will communicate back to the RP2 Leadership team.

As the RP2 program comes to an end, the next steps for the Tracking & Evaluation team include:

- Monitor program progress through bimonthly evaluation surveys and reports will be completed every six months.
- Distribute a Sustainability survey (six months post-project) to assess the longer-term impacts of the pilot projects, including any sustained project activities and other achievements that stemmed from the pilot project (additional external funding, new partnerships, etc.).

Figure 2. Feedback loops between T&E team, RP2 leadership team, and RP2 awardees

Data collected from Jan. 1, 2023 to Jun. 30, 2023. See Appendix for list of projects and timepoints included in the report.

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Projects Reporting

25

Projects Awarded

Projects by Cycle

Latest Survey Completed by Projects

Inactive Projects

Projects from Minority-Serving Institutions

Communities Served

53

Underserved Communities

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COVID-19-Vulnerable Communities

Underserved Communities

COVID-19-Vulnerable Communities

Partner Organization Types

51

Partner Organizations

Partner Organizations by Type

Testing

10

Projects Reporting

Tests Kits Used by Projects

2,969

Total Tests Administered in 2023

5.3%

Positive Tests

Challenges

23

Challenges Reported

Type of Challenges Reported by Projects

Research Products

22

Research Products

Type of Research Products Reported by Projects

CDCC Overall

Ease of accessing support

Overall helpfulness

Promptness of support delivery

CDCC Overall Effectiveness

Effectively addressing feedback received from projects

Effectiveness

CDCC Services

12

Projects Reporting

CDCC Support Services Used

Most Frequently Used CDCC Support Services

Level of Satisfaction with RP2 Admin and Leadership

Level of Satisfaction with Comms

Level of Satisfaction with Testing Support

Level of Satisfaction with Testing Procurement

Level of Satisfaction with WGs

Level of Satisfaction with CCPH

CDCC Impact

The CDCC support services increased my project's understanding of community engagement approaches

The CDCC support services increased my project's application of community-engagement approaches in connecting with my project's communities

The knowledge gained from the CCPH office hours was useful for my project

Pilot Award Impacts

The RP2 Closeout Evaluation survey assesses project outcomes and impacts of the pilot award on the project team and the communities they engaged. The following section highlights key findings from the projects that have completed their Closeout survey at the time of this report.

When asked to rate the impact that the Pilot award had on different aspects of each project's work...

- 100% of projects said that the award improved or significantly improved team collaboration, research methods, and engagement with community stakeholders.
- Over 85% of projects said that the award improved or significantly improved addressing barriers to effective testing in their community.

RADx-UP pilot award impact on the following aspects of your work? (n= 7 projects reporting)

Future Research Products

As more projects are closing out their work, they are developing products to report on their findings.

- The majority of products being developed by projects include peer-reviewed publications and conference presentations (6, or 85.7% of projects have developed at least one peer-reviewed publication and conference presentation)
- Followed by grant proposals to secure additional funding to continue the work (3, or 42.9% of projects have developed at least one grant proposal)

Rapid Research Pilot Program: A Summary of TSBM Outcomes

The Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2) has funded 25 projects, enrolling a total of 2,461 in 2023 and administering 2,969 COVID-19 tests in 2023.

Translational Science Benefits Model³
IMPACT PROFILE

The Impact

The RP2 funded projects resulted in clinical, community & public health, policy and economic benefits.

Through innovative testing technologies, investigative and diagnostic procedures, and community health services and education, projects increased access to and uptake of diagnostic COVID-19 testing in communities of underserved and vulnerable populations.

The Challenge

Communities across the United States are disproportionately impacted by COVID-19, with many underserved and vulnerable communities' facing barriers to COVID-19 testing and diagnosis.

COVID-19 testing, isolation, contact tracing, among others, in communities will help decrease COVID-19 transmission and save lives.

The Approach

RP2 provides Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) subawards to increase the capacity for COVID-19 testing expertise within the community. Increasing training, education, communication, information dissemination, and capacity building related to COVID-19 testing, isolation, contact tracing, among others, in communities will increase our ability to decrease COVID-19 transmission and save lives.

The goal of the program is to improve access to and uptake of diagnostic COVID-19 testing in underserved, COVID-19 medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable populations

The T&E team employs the core components of the Translational Science Benefits (TSBM) Model³ to assess the translation of innovation related to COVID-19 testing into clinical applications, healthcare guidelines, community interventions, policies, and other outcomes that benefit underserved communities at large.

Key Benefits

CLINICAL

Software Technologies. Software installed on mobile devices for diagnosing and tracking care for community members to better manage their own health.

CLINICAL

Investigative and Diagnostic procedures. Methods used in clinical studies to assess the safety, efficacy, and effectiveness of COVID-19 testing methods.

COMMUNITY

Community Health Services. Community members and org's working together to provide COVID-19 services to the community to increase access to and uptake of COVID-19 testing.

COMMUNITY

Health Education Resources. Tailored resources that inform community members of COVID-19 benefits and risks through targeted delivery.

COMMUNITY

Testing Delivery and Uptake. Assess self-efficacy and feasibility of COVID-19 testing services to improve distribution of services to communities.

The team

Tracking & Evaluation team: G Dave, Tara Carr, Shelly Maras, Valerie Lucas, Taylor Baldwin, Jade Hollars, Rossana Roberts

RP2 Program Administration Team: Tim Veldman, Rachel Kauffman, Nilda Itchon-Ramos

Find out more: [RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Program](#)

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Translational
Science
Benefits Model³
IMPACT PROFILE

Key Benefits: An In-Depth Look

The figure below displays the percentage of projects with which at least one of their outcomes aligns with the four key benefit areas of the TSBM.

Project Outcomes Mapped to TSBM Key Benefit Areas* (n= 11 projects)

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Economic Key Benefits

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References

1. About RADx-UP - RADx-UP. Accessed August 20, 2023. <https://radx-up.org/about/>
2. Rapid Research Pilot Program - RADx-UP. Accessed July 17, 2022. <https://radx-up.org/grants/rapid-research-pilot/>
3. Luke DA, Sarli CC, Suiter AM, et al. The Translational Science Benefits Model: A New Framework for Assessing the Health and Societal Benefits of Clinical and Translational Sciences. *Clin Transl Sci.* 2018;11(1):77-84. doi:10.1111/CTS.12495

Appendix

Tests Kits Used by Projects

Project	Test Kit	Test Type
R0101	TaqPath COVID-19 Combo Kit	PCR
R0102	iHealth COVID-19 Antigen Rapid Test	Rapid Antigen
R0103	Hologic Panther Fusion® SARS-CoV-2 assay	PCR
R0103	LDT Lamp	PCR
R0103	Panther Fusion® SARS-CoV-2 Assay	PCR
R0103	Sofia Quidel Antigen test	Rapid Antigen
R0103	Sofia SARS Antigen Fluorescent Immunoassay (FIA)	Rapid Antigen
R0107	QuickVue At-Home OTC COVID-19 2 Test Kits	Rapid Antigen
R0109	TaqPath COVID-19 Fast PCR Combo Kit 2.0	PCR
R0109	Yale SalivaDirect™ COVID-19 Test	PCR
R0401	FlowFlex COVID-19 Antigen Home Test	Rapid Antigen
R0401	iHealth COVID-19 Antigen Rapid Test	Rapid Antigen
R0401	Sofia 2 Flu + SARS Antigen FIA (flu A/B)	Rapid Antigen
R0401	Status COVID-19/Flu A&B	Rapid Antigen
R0405	LumiraDx Antigen Test	Rapid Antigen
R0405	LumiraDx SARS-CoV-2 Ab Test	Antibody
R0405	TaqPath™ COVID-19 Fast PCR Combo Kit 2.0	PCR
R0406	cobas Liat SARS-CoV-2 & Influenza AB	PCR
R0502	CorDx COVID-19 Ag Test	Rapid Antigen
R0503	iHealth COVID-19 Antigen Rapid Test	Rapid Antigen

Projects Reporting

Project	Cycle	Last Timepoint Completed
R0101	1	16
R0102	1	100
R0103	1	14
R0107	1	14
R0109	1	100
R0401	4	100
R0405	4	12
R0406	4	12
R0408	4	10
R0501	5	8
R0502	5	8
R0503	5	8
R0602	6	2
R0604	6	2

*Timepoint 100 indicates the project has completed their Closeout survey.

Glossary

Inactive Projects: Projects that have not been activated yet.
Active Projects: Projects that have completed required activation steps.

Abbreviation	Minority-Serving Institution
AANAPI-Serving	Asian American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institution
Hispanic-Serving	Hispanic-Serving Institution
HBCU	Historically Black College and University
Non-MSI	Non-Minority-Serving Institution
TCU	Tribal College or University

Underserved Community: Populations that the NIH has identified as being underrepresented in biomedical research and known to experience greater morbidity and mortality because of socioeconomic factors. More information can be found [here](#) and [here](#).

Abbreviation	Underserved Community
AIAN	American Indians/Alaska Natives
Asian	Asian Americans
Black	Blacks/African Americans
Latino	Hispanics/Latinos
NHPI	Native Hawaiians and other Pacific Islanders
Rural	Rural and remote communities; underserved rural populations
SGM	Sexual and gender minorities
LowSES	Socioeconomically disadvantaged populations

COVID-19 Vulnerable Community: Populations that the NIH has identified as being at greater risk of COVID-19 infection and poor health outcomes from COVID-19. More information can be found [here](#).

Abbreviation	COVID-19 Vulnerable Community
Child	Children and adolescents
Cognition	Individuals with cognitive impairment or dementia, or communication disorders
Comorbidities	Individuals with medical comorbidities known to increase risk of severe COVID-19
Congregate Housing	Individuals living in congregate housing such as shelters or residential treatment facilities
Elderly	Community-dwelling older adults
EnvRisk	Communities exposed to high rates of air pollution or other toxic exposures
Homeless	Homeless populations
Immigrants	Migrant and immigrant communities
MentalHealth	Individuals with substance use disorders or serious mental illness
Pregnant	Pregnant and post-partum women
Public Housing	Individuals in overcrowded or public housing
Rural	Rural and remote communities; underserved rural populations
TribalNation	Residents of tribal lands or reservations

Abbreviation	CDCC Service
CCPH	Community Campus Partnerships for Health office hours and community engagement consultations
Comms	Communication support services (e.g. RADx-UP website, myRADxUP home portal, newsletter, project-wide meetings, etc.)
Data Informaticist Support	Data Informaticist support
Data Intake Reviews	Data intake reviews (For CDE uploads)
ERC	Engagement Resource Center
Other	Other
RADx-UP CDCC Data Upload	RADx-UP CDCC Data Upload
RP2 Admin and Leadership	Rapid Research Pilot Program administration and leadership
Statistical Support and Consultations	Statistical support and consultations
Testing Procurement	Testing procurements and vendor management
Testing Support	Testing support and guidance services
WGs	Working Groups